

AGRO TECHNOLOGY OF ESTABLISHING AND MAINTENANCE OF SHUTUT AND BALKI MURBIE ORCHARDS

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ABSTRACT

That is why, before starting a garden, it is necessary to correctly decide the issues of choosing a good land for a garden and placing good seedlings on them. The low height of the plot is of great importance when choosing land for a garden. It is dangerous to create a garden at low altitudes, because in winter, cold air stays for a long time in such places, and the trees are hit by frost. Colds in the mountains kill the flowers of the trees in the lowlands. When choosing land for mulberry gardens, the grain size, fertility and quality of the soil are of great importance. Groundwater should be at least two meters below the surface of the ground in the land to be planted for fruit.

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First of all, when creating a garden, the spacing of trees is of great importance. If the trees are planted densely, then their branches will grow and cross each other, and as a result, the yield will decrease.

Trees grow well when transplanted sparsely, but there are few of them in the garden, and they are often damaged by frost.

The long life of mulberry trees, the beginning of the harvest, how long they produce and the continuous abundant harvest from them depend on the correct selection of the place.

In fact, it is recommended to plant Shotut and Balkhi mulberry trees planted for fruit in one massif on at least 2-3 hectares of land. When creating mulberry groves for a good harvest, it is recommended to make 6x6 m spacing between Shotut trees in northern districts of Uzbekistan, 8x8x m in moderate and southern climate regions, 8 m between rows of Balkhi mulberry trees in northern regions, 10x10 m in moderate and southern climate regions.

2-year-old branched saplings of shotut and Balkhi mulberry are held.

Two-year-old grafted seedlings are also planted in row planting (along ditches, roadsides, and farm plots).

So, when Shotut and Balkhi are planted for mulberry fruit, they can be used for other purposes up to 7-8 years between the rows. For this, short, fast-growing, early-yielding fruit trees are placed between the rows. Also, one-year agricultural crops such as potatoes, tomatoes, cabbage, carrots, melons, watermelons, etc. can be planted between rows for 7-8 years.

It's time to transplant seedlings.

Mulberry seedlings are planted in the fall after the leaves of the trees fall or after the first autumn frost. In the spring, seedlings are planted when the soil is ripe. The best period for mulberry planting is from October 25 to December 1 in autumn.

If the weather is hot in December, planting can be continued until the end of the month, and in summer, from March 1 to April 15.

Preparation of land and seedlings, as well as transplanting.

The roots of the mulberry tree are deep in the soil, so the ground is plowed in the fall to a depth of 60-70 cm.

Shotut and Balkhi mulberry, plowed up with 180-200 kg of phosphorus per hectare before plowing the land in the fall, will be convenient for creating gardens.

Therefore, it is necessary to plow the ground 2-3 weeks before transplanting seedlings in the fall. If the seedlings are planted in the spring, the land is plowed and leveled in the fall, the pits for the seedlings are dug according to plan, that is, they are made as a throne for planting.

Then, at the time of planting seedlings or a few days before planting, pits 70x70 cm wide and 60 cm high are dug in the planting areas.

Before planting, the damaged and rotten ends of the roots of the seedlings are cut with a sharp pruning shears or pruning knife.

Seedlings should be transplanted in such a way that their root neck should be level with the surface of the earth. It is necessary not to allow the roots of transplanted seedlings to be bent together or to form a space around the roots. At the time of planting, fertile soil is first put in the pit, and until the seedlings are transplanted, their branches are cut, leaving 30-40 cm in length, and the surroundings are well covered. Planted seedlings are quickly satiated and watered, and not all transplanted seedlings take hold. That's why the orchards planted with seedlings are checked every year in the fall, and if they don't grow, they are replaced with grafted and grown seedlings in the fall of this year or in the early spring of the next year. Caring for young mulberry trees.

After transplanting seedlings grown as grafts and then planted in the garden, they are watered once every 15-20 days for two to three years.

In the following years, it is watered according to the thirst of the trees. In spring, summer and

autumn, the circumference of mulberry trees is cut at least twice at a depth of 15-20 cm, and the rows are cultivated or plowed. In general, Shotut and Balkhi mulberry trees should be given a six-headed shape. To do this, in each of the three main branches on the head, leaving well-placed branches, others are cut. Every year, in the spring, the branches growing on the trunk and branches are cut to the trunk.

The amount of nitrogen and phosphorus is low in the gray soils of Uzbekistan. Trees grow better when organic and mineral fertilizers are added to these lands. When the trees begin to bear fruit, their growth slows down a bit, and instead of growth buds, more buds develop. That is why the demand for fertilizers increases year by year.

120 kg of phosphorus and 40 kg of potassium are applied to each hectare of the harvested Shotut and Balkhi mulberry orchards at a depth of 18-20 cm in two periods from both sides of the furrow. 75% of these will be given in early spring, 25% in late May and early July.

In order to improve the quality of shotut and Balkhi mulberry fruits, instead of nitrogen mineral fertilizers, it is recommended to apply organic fertilizers in the amount of 20-40 t per hectare every two years before plowing the land.

In the fruit-bearing Shotut and Balkhi mulberry orchards, broken and dry branches of the trees are cut off every year before the aphid movement begins.

Therefore, the base of the trees is loosened 2-3 times a year and watered from 3 to 7-8 times depending on the soil conditions.

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